

ACTIN-BASED TRANSPORT ADAPTS POLARITY DOMAIN SIZE TO LOCAL CELLULAR CURVATURE

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SUMMARY

Intracellular structures and organelles such as the nucleus, the centrosome or the mitotic spindle typically scale their size to cell size [1]. Similarly, cortical polarity domains built around the active form of conserved Rho-GTPases, such as Cdc42p, exhibit widths that may range over 2 orders of magnitudes in cells with different sizes and shapes [2-6]. The establishment of such domains, typically involves positive feedback loops based on reaction-diffusion and/or actin-mediated vesicle transport [3, 7, 8]. How these elements may adapt polarity domain size to cellular geometry is not known. Here, by tracking the width of successive oscillating Cdc42-GTP domains in fission yeast spores [9], we find that domain width scales with local cell surface radii of curvature over an 8-fold range, independently of absolute cell volume, surface or Cdc42-GTP concentration. This local scaling requires formin-nucleated cortical actin cables and the fusion of secretory vesicles transported along these cables with the membrane. These data suggest that reaction-diffusion may set a minimal domain size, and that secretory vesicle transport along actin cables may dilute and extend polarity domains to adapt their size to local cell surface curvature. This work reveals that actin networks may act as micrometric curvature sensors, and uncovers a generic morphogenetic principle for how polarity domains define their size according to cell morphologies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cdc42-GTP polarity domains scale their width to local cell surface curvature.

To understand how cells may control the size of a polarity domain, we exploited the oscillatory dynamics of active Cdc42-GTP polar domains/caps in the early development of fission yeast spores, which occurs within an extended G1 phase [9] (Movie S1). We took images of fields of spores expressing CRIB-3GFP, a marker for Cdc42-GTP [10], and developed a semi-automatic script to selectively analyze spores with single domains, and compute the full width at half maximum of the domain, FWHM, from a Gaussian fit of the CRIB-3GFP intensity profile along the cell surface [11-13] (Figure 1A and Figure S1A-S1E).

In wild-type (WT) spores, which come with natural variations in shapes and sizes, we found an interesting positive correlation between domain width and cellular local radius of curvature, R_c , measured around the domain ($R^2 = 0.59$) (Figure S1F and S1G). This correlation was well represented by a linear scaling such that: $\text{FWHM} = 0.97\mu\text{m} + 1.30 * R_c$ ($n=110$ domains, Fitting accuracy: $R^2 = 0.35$) (Figure 1B). Cdc42 visualized with a functional sandwich GFP fusion, as well as the Cdc42 GEF *scd1p*, the scaffold protein *scd2p*, and other upstream polarity components formed domains that followed similar size-scaling, with slightly different slopes between markers [9, 14, 15] (Figures S1H and S1I). Importantly, given that the oscillatory dynamics of these domains is much faster than shape changes in those spores, these scaling relationships predominantly reflect an adaptation of domain size to cell geometry, rather than a change in local shape consequent to persistent growth around the site of Cdc42-GTP accumulation [4, 16] (Figure S1J and Movie S1). 3D reconstructions revealed that domains had circular shapes in most

instances, although we did observe a fraction of ellipsoidal domains in spores with flattened 3D shapes. The major axes of these ellipsoidal domains appeared to scale with corresponding principal radii of curvature in 3D (Figure S2A). Analysis of spores of the Rho GAP mutants *rga4Δ* and *rga2Δ*, which are respectively bigger and smaller than WT spores [9], allowed to extend the range of validity of this scaling, and suggested that domain width scaling was independent of fine-tuned Cdc42 activity (Figure 1B) [4, 10, 17].

To directly manipulate local curvature independently of cell size, we first deformed spores in microfabricated wells or linear micro-channels [18-20]. Domains became small when assembling at the curved tip and large when forming on the flat side of deformed spores (Figure 1C and Figure S2B). These experiments showed that domain size was only weakly correlated with cell volume ($R^2= 0.22$), surface area ($R^2= 0.23$), and uncorrelated with absolute CRIB-3GFP intensity at the cap ($R^2=-0.03$) (Figure S2C). Secondly, we analyzed domain size in early repolarizing WT spheroplasts [16, 21]. Those spheroplasts come with similar volumes as vegetative cells, but significantly larger radii of curvature at the site of Cdc42-GTP domain assembly. Domains were much larger than those found at cell tips of control cells, and also scaled with R_c , suggesting this effect is not a particular property of spores (Figure 1D).

We then tested if this scaling remained valid during polarized growth, such as after spore or spheroplast outgrowth, when polarity becomes stable to promote tube extension [9, 16]. Using time-lapses, we found that domain size scaled with R_c at each time point from typically 2-3h before until 2-3h after outgrowth. The robustness of the scaling was particularly striking close to

outgrowth, when the pointy tip emerged out of the spore or spheroplast body, as R_c rapidly transitioned from large to small values, to eventually plateau at a value half of the typical WT diameter [9, 16] (Figure 1E). These results suggest that the diameter of emerging polar tubes is not firmly pre-set by the size of Cdc42-GTP domains before tube emergence, but rather relies on more dynamic crosstalk between geometry and domain size, or other unknown elements (Figure S2D) [4, 16]. Accordingly, by manipulating the diameter of polarized vegetative WT cells in microchannels, we could generate cells with diameters much smaller than controls, which exhibited smaller Cdc42-GTP domains well-scaled to curvature radii at the tips (Figure 1F). We conclude that domain size adaptation to local curvature also applies to stable polar growth situations.

Pulling together those different conditions, we validated domain sizing over almost an 8-fold range (from $R_c = 0.80 \mu\text{m}$ to $R_c = 6.23 \mu\text{m}$), with an overall scaling-law following: $\text{FWHM} = 0.81 \mu\text{m} + 1.42 * R_c$ ($n=557$ domains, Fitting accuracy: $R^2 = 0.68$) (Figure S2E). Thus, Cdc42-GTP domains can probe local surface geometry to adapt their width to micrometric cellular curvatures.

Secretory vesicle transport along actin cables adapts domain size to local curvature

Cytoskeleton polymers may contribute to the assembly and maintenance of polarity domains [14]. Although microtubule depolymerization did not impact domain size and scaling; we found that complete actin disassembly with $100 \mu\text{M}$ Latrunculin A (LatA) had a major impact on domain size. Cdc42-GTP domains still oscillated [9], and were polarized in similar fraction as in controls, but were significantly smaller. Importantly, these LatA-treated domains did not adapt their widths to

curvature, but remained small independently of cell geometry ($R^2= 0.01$) (Figure 2A-2C, 3C and Figure S3A). Dynamic LatA wash-in caused domains to shrink to a minimal size independent of their initial width. Conversely, LatA wash-outs yielded domain expansion, and width recovery adapted to local curvature (Figure 2D-2E).

In yeast, actin contributes to Cdc42 polarity, by regulating Cdc42 endocytosis at Arp2/3-nucleated actin patches and secretory vesicle transport along formin-nucleated cables that carry Cdc42 and/or other factors towards the membrane [14]. In *for3Δ* spores, which lack for3-nucleated actin cables, Cdc42-GTP domain size was smaller than WT, and did not scale with local curvature ($R^2=-0.01$). A *sec8-1* mutant, which strongly reduces secretory vesicle fusion at restrictive temperature [22, 23], displayed a similar phenotype as *for3Δ*, with even smaller domains (Figure 3A-3C and Figure S3A-S3C). In contrast, endocytosis did not impact domain scaling, as tested with various endocytic mutants or with short-time treatment with 100μM of CK666, which disrupts actin patches (Figure 3C and Figure S3D) [24]. Altogether, these results suggest that an actin-independent system may assemble domains with a minimal size and that secretory vesicles transport along actin cables and their fusion at the membrane may extend polarity domains to scale them to local curvature.

Vesicle transport and fusion may dilute Cdc42-GTP domains in a curvature-dependent manner

How vesicle transport and fusion may contribute to Cdc42 polarization is still debated. One model posits that vesicles may deliver more Cdc42 to the domain [3], while another suggests that vesicle fusion may instead dilute polar domains [25]. Recent work has challenged the delivery model, by

showing that a Cdc42 allele, Cdc42^{SW-rit^C}, that is not trafficked on secretory vesicles is still capable of spontaneous Cdc42-GTP polarization [15]. In this allele, we found that domains still adapted their width to local curvature, with a scaling close to the WT situation. LatA treatment caused similar shrinkage and loss of scaling as in WT (Figure 3D-3E and Figure S3E-S3F). Thus, the traffic of Cdc42 itself on secretory vesicles is dispensable for domain size adaptation to local curvature.

To test if vesicle transport and fusion may rather dilute polarity domains we compared Cdc42-GTP concentration in subsequent domains, formed at different locations in the same spore using time-lapses. We found that a transition from a first, narrow domain assembled on a curved region, to a second, large domain formed on a flatter region, was accompanied by a significant decrease in CRIB signal. Conversely, a transition from a large to a narrow domain yielded an increase in CRIB signal (Figure 3F-3G). These findings are consistent with a mechanism in which vesicle transport and fusion may dilute and extend Cdc42-GTP domains in a curvature-dependent manner.

A model based on the limitation of vesicle transport by the surface scanned by actin cables may explain domain size adaptation to local curvature.

We next visualized actin cables associated with Cdc42-GTP domains [26]. Actin cables had wiggly appearance, with varying lengths and were quite dynamic, with a typical turn-over of tens of seconds (Figure S4A). Notably, 3D analysis revealed that the vast majority of cables were restricted to a cortical region within 0.4 μ m underneath the plasma membrane, in agreement with

a previous report in budding yeast (Figure 4A-4C, S4B and Movie S2) [27]. This cortical actin cable arrangement may thus represent an optimal configuration to probe cell surface geometry.

Actin cable nucleation by the formin for3p did not appear to be sensitive to curvature. For3-3GFP exhibited a dotted pattern clustered in a single domain, which scaled with R_c (Figure 4D). To estimate cable number and length distributions we treated cells with CK666, which does not influence domain sizing at short time-scale (Figure 3C), to selectively disassemble patches that obscure the visualization of cables, and imaged after 5 min. [24]. In agreement with for3-3GFP results, the number of actin cables connected to the polarity domain, increased on average with R_c (Figure 4E). Actin cable lengths, computed in 3D, followed similar distributions independently of local curvature (Figure 4F). Together these results suggest that in varying spore surface geometries, actin cable networks may grow with similar nucleation density, stability and length distribution.

Given that cortical actin cables turn-over within seconds, and that polarity domains establish within minutes, the network of cables associated with Cdc42-GTP caps may scan on average a dome-like surface, which depends on cable length distribution and local surface geometry. Simple mathematical analysis suggested that the surface covered by these “domes” displayed a steady increase with R_c in the range of curvature radii and cable length measured in spores (Figure 4C, 4G, 4H, Figure S4B and Supplemental model). Given this, we propose a simple geometrical model for cap size adaptation to local geometry based on four components (Figure 4H): (1) Actin cables dynamically radiate from sites of Cdc42-GTP accumulation along the surface, and have a length

distribution independent of curvature (observation, mechanism unknown). (2) Vesicles flux toward the cap increases with the area scanned by actin domes (hypothesis). (3) Cdc42-GTP caps are built by an actin-independent system and diluted by secretory vesicles (observation). (4) Dilution extends the cap in proportion to vesicle flux (hypothesis, supported by previous theoretical work [28]).

In sum, our quantitative analyses of oscillating Cdc42-GTP caps in fission yeast spores serve to define mechanisms for how cortical domains may set their size with respect to cellular geometry. Domains can still assemble without actin, most likely through reaction-diffusion, and have a minimal size independent of curvature [29]. In these spores, actin is thus dispensable for spontaneous Cdc42 polarization [8, 15], but may function primarily to adapt domain size to local cell geometry. We propose that actin cable network growth on differently curved surfaces may yield sufficient variations in the surface scanned by the network to influence the flux of secretory vesicles back to the domain and consequent domain sizing. Thus, in our view, curvature sensing is not encoded at the level of cytoskeleton polymer structural properties [30], but rather as a result of self-organization of the network on a given surface geometry [31].

While recent studies have suggested that the fission yeast diameter is set by the size of Cdc42-GTP domains [4, 16], our data refine these views, and demonstrate that domains can also rapidly adapt to cell morphology, highlighting novel functional interplays between shape and polarity [18, 20]. Accordingly, recent theoretical models predict the existence of stability conditions on the adaptation of Cdc42-GTP domain size to cell geometry required to maintain a stable diameter over

generations of dividing cells [12]. Finally, by analyzing images of active-Cdc42 domains in other cell types we found that our scaling could be valid over a 100-fold range in radii of curvature (Figure S4C-S4D) [2-6]. Because most eukaryotic cells share the use of Rho GTPases and actin-based systems to cluster functional cortical domains, our study may have uncovered a novel generic design for morphogenesis.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

DB, AH, DD and NM performed experiments, HT developed image analysis scripts, DB, AH, DS and NM designed the experiments. DB, AH, HT and NM wrote the manuscript.

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Figure 1. Cdc42-GTP polar domains/caps scale their widths to local cellular radius of curvature.

(A) (Top) Confocal time-lapse of a germinating WT spore expressing CRIB-3GFP. The red dotted line indicates the line scan used to compute fluorescence intensity. (Bottom) Intensity profiles (red dots) and Gaussian fits (blue line) for each time frame of the above time-lapse. The blue double-headed arrow indicates the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the Gaussian fit. (B) (Top) Confocal single slice images of WT (red), *rga2Δ* (green) and *rga4Δ* (purple) spores. The white arrow and circle represent the fitting used to compute local radius of curvature, R_c . (Bottom) CRIB-3GFP domain FWHM plotted as a function of R_c , for *rga2Δ* (n=52), WT (n=110) and *rga4Δ* (n=45). (C) (Top) Confocal single slice images of spores deformed in microfabricated wells (WT, orange) and microchannels (*rga4Δ*, red). (Bottom) CRIB-3GFP domain FWHM plotted as a function of R_c , for WT controls (n=11) and deformed (n=41), *rga4Δ* controls (n=50) and deformed (n=40). (D) (Top) Confocal images of re-polarizing WT spheroplasts. (Bottom) CRIB-3GFP domain FWHM plotted as a function of R_c , for WT spheroplasts (n=60) and spores (n=110). (E) (Left) Confocal time-lapse of outgrowing WT spores expressing CRIB-3GFP. (Right top) Evolution of CRIB-3GFP FWHM as a function of time for 3 outgrowing spores. (Inset) Evolution of R_c as a function of time for the same spores. (Right bottom) CRIB-3GFP domain FWHM plotted as a function of R_c , for different time points before and after outgrowth for WT spheroplasts (n=2 cells) and spores (n=8 cells) (F) (Top) Confocal single slice images of undeformed (green) and deformed (light blue) WT cells grown in microchannels. (Bottom) Plot of CRIB-3GFP domain FWHM as a function of R_c , for WT cells outside channels (n=26), undeformed inside channels (n=18) and deformed inside channels (n=56). Scale bars, 2 μ m.

Figure 2: Actin mediates polar domain size scaling to cellular curvature.

(A) Merged stacks of WT spores expressing CRIB-3GFP and LifeAct-mCherry treated with DMSO (red) or 100 μ M Latrunculin A (LatA) (blue). (B) Plot of CRIB-3GFP FWHM as a function of R_c , for controls (n=110) and spores treated with LatA for 30 min in bulk (n=52). Dotted lines represent corresponding linear fits with slopes, s (C) (Top) Confocal single slice images of LatA-treated WT spores expressing Scd1-3GFP or Scd2-GFP. Arrowheads mark polar domains. (Bottom) Linear regression slopes, s , for CRIB-3GFP, Scd1-3GFP and Scd2-GFP, in controls (n=110, for CRIB-3GFP; n=39, for Scd1-3GFP; n=14, for Scd2-GFP) and LatA-treated spores

(n=52, for CRIB-GFP; n=30 for Scd1-3GFP; n=30, for Scd2-GFP). Error bars represent standard deviation of regression values. ** Student T-test $p < 10^{-5}$ (D) (Top) Confocal time-lapse of a spore expressing CRIB-3GFP, 10 min before and 30 min after LatA treatment. (Bottom) Evolution of CRIB-3GFP domain FWHM as a function of time, following LatA wash-in for 12 individual WT spores. (E) (Top) Confocal time-lapse of a spore expressing CRIB-3GFP, before LatA treatment, 30 min after LatA wash in and 90 min after wash out. (Bottom) Evolution of CRIB-3GFP domain FWHM as a function of time, following LatA treatment and wash out for 10 individual wild-type spores. Scale bars, 1 μm .

Figure 3: Actin cables-based secretory vesicle transport and fusion may dilute polarity domains to scale them to local curvature

(A) Confocal images of WT, *for3Δ* and *sec8-1* (37°C) spores expressing CRIB-3GFP. (B) Polarity domain sizes for control WT (n=110), WT treated with LatA (n=52), *sec8-1* (n=131) and *for3Δ* spores (n=108). (C) Linear regression slopes, s , of CRIB-3GFP domain size scaling as a function of R_c , in the indicated mutants and drug treatments (n>30 for each condition). Error bars represent standard deviation. (D) (Top) Confocal mid-plane images of CRIB-3GFP-expressing spores carrying the Cdc42-mCherry^{SW} (blue) or Cdc42-mCherry^{SW-rit^C} (red) allele. (Bottom) Plot of CRIB-3GFP domain FWHM as a function of R_c , for Cdc42-mCherry^{SW} (n=42) and Cdc42^{SW-rit^C} (n=77) spores. (E) (Top) Confocal images of Cdc42-mCherry^{SW-rit^C} spores expressing CRIB-3GFP treated with DMSO (green) or LatA (light blue). (Bottom) Linear regression slopes, s , for Cdc42-mCherry^{SW} (n=42), Cdc42-mCherry^{SW-rit^C} (n=77), Cdc42-mCherry^{SW-rit^C} + DMSO (n=22) and Cdc42^{SW-rit^C} + LatA (n=43) spores. (F) (Top) Confocal single-slice time-lapse of two individual WT spores expressing CRIB-3GFP, taken at 0 and 30 min, normalized in the same manner. (Bottom) Corresponding intensity profiles (red dots) and Gaussian fits (blue line) for each time frame of the above time-lapse. The blue and green double-headed arrows indicate FWHM and peak height (PH) of the Gaussian fit, respectively. (G) Ratio of peak height between 0 min and 30 min (PH₀/PH₃₀) plotted against ratio of FWHM ratio (FWHM₀/FWHM₃₀), for n=22 individual spores. Quadrants of the plot correspond to dilution of CRIB signal in the cap (light grey) or concentration of CRIB signal in the cap (dark grey). ** Student T-test $p < 10^{-5}$. Scale bars, 2 μm .

Figure 4: Cortical actin-cable networks may probe local cell surface geometry to scale polarity domains to local radii of curvature. (A) Confocal slices of spores expressing LifeAct-mCherry, at the bottom, mid and top focal plane. White arrowheads point at actin cables. (B) Actin cables localization, for spores and cells ($n > 10$ in each condition). (C) 3D rendering of a WT spore expressing LifeAct-mCherry and CRIB-3GFP, 5 min after CK666 treatment. (D) (Top left) Single mid-focal confocal image of a WT spore expressing For3-3GFP; (Bottom left) Corresponding temporally averaged picture, obtained by a projection of 30 single images taken every 1 sec. (Right) For3-3GFP domain FWHM plotted as a function of R_c , quantified from temporally averaged For3-3GFP domains ($n = 62$). (E) Number of actin cables connected to Cdc42-GTP caps as a function of R_c in WT spores ($n = 10$ spores and 141 cables). (F) Distribution of actin cable length connected to Cdc42-GTP domains binned with respect to R_c ($n = 21$ spores and 296 cables). (G) Evolution of actin dome's surface as a function of R_c mathematically computed and weighted to account for cables length distribution measured in 4F. (H) Deformation of actin networks growing on a surface with a given geometry may account for polarity domain size adaptation to local curvature: An initial Cdc42-GTP domain with minimal size is assembled by reaction-diffusion; actin cables then grow from this domain following the curvature of the local surface and define over time a dome-like network from where they fetch vesicles that move back to the domain along cables. Fusion of these vesicles expand the Cdc42-GTP domain via a dilution mechanism. The surface explored by these actin cables over time may influence the flux of vesicles carried back to the domain. As a consequence, an actin networks grown on a flat surface may bring more vesicles to the domain than on a curved surface, yielding a broader polarity domain. Error bars represent standard deviation. Scale bars, $1 \mu\text{m}$.

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Figure 4

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Figure S1

Figure S1 related to Figure 1: Image analysis and selection of polarized spores; and domain

scaling of different polarity factors. (A) Sample selection based on the 1D CRIB intensity profile along the cell contour. Spores with a single polarity domain (left) are selected and those with more than one polarity domain (middle) or without polarity domains (right) are discarded in a semi-automated manner. (Top) Mid-focal plane image of CRIB-3GFP distribution and cell contour (red broken line). (Bottom) Plot of 1D CRIB intensity profile. The intensity profile at the single polarity domain (left) is well approximated by a Gaussian function (red broken line). **(B)** (Left) Proportions of polarized spores, spores with split domains and non-polarized spores in WT. (Right) Fraction of single polarized spores faithfully analyzed by the script. **(C-E)** Parameter selection in the analysis of 1D CRIB intensity profile. **(C)** CRIB signal at the cell membrane was computed using different thicknesses around cell contour: 0.085 (blue), 0.42 (red), and 0.85 (green) μm . **(D)** Gaussian fitting for each thickness from (C), with corresponding colors. **(E)** Evolution of FWHM computed for the same spore as a function of thickness. **(F and G)** Parameter selection in the analysis of cell local curvature. **(F)** Circle fit of polar domain shape with different fit area of 1 (blue), 3 (red), and 5 μm (green). Black solid line: cell outline, broken color line: circle fit, bold color line: cell contour region used for the fit. **(G)** Local curvature radius of polar domain computed for the same spore as a function of fitting region length. **(H)** Domain FWHM scaling with R_c formed by different upstream polarity factors with local radius of curvature. From left to right: Cdc42-sfGFP^{SW} (n=15), Scd1-3GFP (n=39), Scd2-GFP (n=14) and GFP-Bgs4 (n=20). Top: Representative confocal mid-plane images of spores expressing the indicated markers with a blue dotted line to mark the cell contour. Bottom: Polarity domain FWHM plotted as a function of R_c . Dotted lines depict linear regression fits. **(I)** Two by two co-scaling of domains size formed by different upstream polarity factors with local radii of curvature. (Left Top) Confocal mid-plane images of a spore expressing CRIB-3GFP and Bud6-Tomato. (Left Bottom) Confocal mid-plane images of a spore expressing CRIB-3GFP and RFP-Bgs4. (Right) Ratio of polar domain FWHM obtained from each spores co-expressing CRIB-3GFP and Bud6-Tomato (n=30) or CRIB-3GFP and RFP-Bgs4 (n=19). **(J)** Measurement of local curvature before, during and after the establishment of a single CRIB domain in WT spores. (Top) Representative spore time-lapse. Arrowheads point to analyzed region. (Bottom) Quantification of curvature radius changes at different stages of domain polarization for 17 individual spores represented with different colors.

Figure S2

Figure S2 related to Figure 1: 3D organization of polarity domains; dynamic of polarity domain in deformed spores; Dependence of polarity domains size on cell volume, surface, CRIB concentration; CRIB FWHM does not preset tip curvature during outgrowth; and validation of domain sizing over multiple conditions.

(A) 3D reconstructions of confocal stacks of wild-type spores expressing CRIB-3GFP with different geometries. Side view, front view and segmented front view are shown for each cell. (B) Confocal time-lapse of spores expressing CRIB-3GFP deformed in microfabricated devices. (Top) Two WT spores in a microwell. (Bottom) *rga4Δ* spore in a longitudinal microchannel. Arrowheads mark pole caps. (C) Plot of CRIB-3GFP polarity domain FWHM as a function of CRIB-3GFP intensity at the cap, cell volume and cell surface in wild-type spores (n=105). (D) The size of CRIB domain does not firmly preset the diameter of emerging tubes at outgrowth: Correlation coefficient, R^2 , between CRIB FWHM measured 1h before outgrowth and R_c at various times before and after outgrowth for time-lapses of 8 spores and 2 spheroplasts used in Figure 1E. (E) Combined data of polarity domain FWHM plotted as a function of R_c , for all indicated conditions (n=557 domains). The dotted line depicts the linear regression fit. Scale bars, 2 μm .

Figure S3

Figure S3 related to Figure 3: Scaling analysis in conditions that influence endocytosis and vesicle trafficking; and scaling analysis of Cdc42^{SW}-rit^C allele. (A) Proportions of polarized spores, spores with split domains and non-polarized spores of WT, WT treated with LatA, *for3Δ* and *sec8-1* (at 37°C). **(B)** Plot of CRIB-3GFP polarity domain FWHM plotted as a function of R_c , for wild-type (n=110) and *for3Δ* (n=108) spores, indicated in red and green respectively. **(C)** Plot of CRIB-3GFP polarity domain FWHM as a function of R_c , for wild-type (n=69) and *sec8-1* (n=131) spores grown at 37°C, indicated in red and light blue respectively. **(D)** Plot of CRIB-3GFP polarity domain FWHM as a function of R_c , for wild-type (n=110), CK666-treated wild-type (n=63), *end4Δ* (n=76) and *wsp1Δ* (n=32) spores, indicated in red, green, purple and blue respectively. **(E)** Proportions of polarized spores, spores with split domains and non-polarized spores of Cdc42^{SW}-rit^C treated with DMSO or LatA. **(F)** Plot of CRIB-3GFP polarity domain FWHM plotted as a function of R_c , for Cdc42^{SW}-rit^C spores treated with DMSO (n=22) or LatA (n=43), indicated in red and blue respectively. Dotted lines in (B), (C), (D) and (F) correspond to linear fits.

Figure S4

Figure S4 related to Figure 4: Actin cable dynamics and organization; and active-Cdc42 domain scaling in other cell types. (A) Confocal time-lapse of a wild-type spore expressing CRIB-3GFP and LifeAct-mCherry. LifeAct images are maximal projections of confocal z-stacks taken at 0.2 μm interval. Arrows indicate the end of a growing actin cable. (B) Maximal projection of confocal stacks of wild-type spores expressing CRIB-3GFP and LifeAct-mCherry with different geometries, either untreated or treated with CK-666 for 5 min. (C) Active-Cdc42 domains in fission yeast spores and spheroplast and in a polarized leader cell at the front of a migrating MDCK cell monolayer. Scale bars, 3 μm . (D) Active-Cdc42 domain FWHM plotted as a function of local radius of curvature for indicated cell types and situations. The dotted square delineates the zoomed area for the plot depicted on the right. Data for Neurospora spores come from images in [S1] and those for mouse oocytes from [S2]. We note that radius of curvature was determined using the same script for MDCK; and this analysis may be prone to uncertainty given the more irregular shapes of the plasma membrane in these cells.

SUPPLEMENTAL EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Yeast Strains, Media, and Genetic Methods

Standard methods for *S. pombe* media and genetic manipulations were used (<http://www-bcf.usc.edu/~forsburg/>). Strains used in this study are listed below. Spores were obtained from homothallic h90 strains. Freshly growing cells were sporulated on malt extract (ME) solid media for at least 3 days. Spores were then digested overnight at room temperature in 1/200 glusulase solution in water to kill vegetative cells and the enzyme was washed out 3 times in water. For measurements of local radii of curvature and domain widths in spores, spores were germinated and grown in liquid YE5S for 4-5 h at 25°C or 3-4h at 30°C before imaging. Spores carrying the allele Cdc42-mCherry^{SW}-Rit^C, which we found to be partially defective in mating, were digested overnight and grown 5-6h at 25°C before imaging.

Pharmacological Inhibitors

Methyl-2-benzimidazole carbamate (MBC, Aldrich) was used at a final concentration of 50µg/ml from a 100X stock solution made fresh in DMSO. Latrunculin A (LatA, Sigma) was used at a final concentration of 100µM from a 100X stock in DMSO. CK666 (Tocris Bioscience) was used at a final concentration of 100µM from a 100X stock in DMSO.

Microscopy

For long-term imaging, spores were placed on 2% agar YE5S pads and covered with a coverslip. For inhibitor flow through treatments, spores were placed in home-made glass channels coated with poly-lysine and lectin. Spores were imaged at room temperature (23°C –25°C), with controlled humidity, with an inverted Spinning-Disk confocal microscope provided with a motorized stage and automatic focus (Nikon Ti-Eclipse), and an EM-CCD camera (Hamamatsu). Images were generally acquired with a 100X oil immersion objective (Nikon CFI Plan Apo DM 100x 1.4 NA) with a 2.5X magnifying lens or 100x objective alone. Images of CRIB-3GFP were acquired at the mid focal plane unless stated otherwise. For reasons that may relate to findings presented in [S3], most single CRIB domains are close to the mid-focal plane when spores are imaged between glass slides and coverslips or agar pad and coverslips.

Analysis of z-stacks showed that small out of focus calculation of FWHM may be a source of error that we estimate to be smaller than 20%. 3D analysis of CRIB-3GFP and LifeAct-mCherry were performed by acquiring 26 z-stacks with a 0.2 μ m step. Time-lapses for spheroplast outgrowth were performed by acquiring 12 z-stacks.

Quantifications of CRIB intensity for dilution assay (Figure 3G) were performed with confocal single mid-focal plane time-lapses with 30min intervals; measured peak heights were corrected for photobleaching.

Image analysis

To analyze polarity domain width and curvature, we developed a Matlab package “CurvPol” that we make available to the community. This script starts from a path to a data folder containing many fields of many spores or cells. The script interacts with the user; and first displays a large image of the field and asks how many spores have to be analyzed. The user then draws one ROI around each spore, and one for the background. The script displays a large view of the fluorescent image of the spore expressing CRIB-3GFP (or any other marker) and the user places 20 points around the cell edge following the fluorescence. We confirmed that adding more points did not improve neither analyses of cell shape nor polarity domain size. These discrete points are interpolated using cubic spline method, with an interval of interpolation of one pixel, to smooth the cell contour. Along the determined cell contour, a one dimensional profile of polarity factors’ intensity is computed by integrating the fluorescence signal in a direction perpendicular to the cell contour. The integral area (thickness of cell edge) can be varied in the initial settings and had little effect on the result for CRIB signals (Figure S1 C-E). As a default value for all analysis on CRIB presented in the paper the thickness used was 2px. For other markers, like for3-3GFP and bud6-tomato, which are dottier and more weakly associated to the membrane, we used a 8px thickness. Based on the 1D signal profile, singularly polarized spores were selected and analyzed further automatically (see ‘Data selection’ hereafter).

To define the size of polarity domains, the script first searches for the position with the highest signal intensity along the cell contour. Then the signal profile around the peak is fitted with a Gaussian function (Figure S1A left) [S4-S6]. We note that spores pose more challenge to analyze

than vegetative cells due to much lower fluorescent signals [S3]. For images acquired at 250x magnification a default of 60 points ($\sim 2.6 \mu\text{m}$) were used for the fit. The domain size was determined as the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the fitted Gaussian function. Fitting parameters (number of points for the fit and initial width for fitting search) can be changed in the script. As noted above, the outcome was robust against the choice of parameters. In addition, if a fit appears to be off the actual data, the software allows the user to place the analyzed cell in a category for re-analysis, which can be subsequently performed by modifying fitting parameters.

To define cell local curvature at the polar cap, a small number of cell contour points were fitted with a circle. The center of these points was determined as the center of the fitted Gaussian function, and a default of $3 \mu\text{m}$ contour (~ 70 points at 250x) around the center were used to compute local curvature radius (Figure S1F). This length can be modified in the script input; and in events of unsatisfactory curvature fitting, the user can again place the analyzed cell in a category for re-analysis which can be performed by modifying this length. We found that varying this length between $1\text{-}5 \mu\text{m}$ did not largely influence the result (Figure S1F and S1G).

Data selection

Polarized spores were selected in an unbiased manner with this script (Figure S1A). The selection was based on the 1D intensity profile of polarity factors at the cell membrane. The first polar domain was identified by Gaussian fitting around the point with the highest intensity. If the fitting was bad (characterized by a failure in the regression), the data was automatically defined as ‘non-polarized’. We note that most of the data classified in this category are non-polarized spores or polarized spores with very low signal. To discard spores with multiple domains, the same domain identification was performed from the 1D intensity profile, in which the first domain approximated by the Gaussian function was subtracted. The ratio of second to first peaks was used to define single vs multipole domains. A threshold for the second/first ratio was introduced and data with higher ratio value than the threshold were categorized as multi-domains spores (Figure S1A). After analysis, the software display the relevant selection numbers (second/first peak height and Gaussian fitting accuracy R^2 value), together with the image, raw plot and Gaussian fit and asks the user if the analysis is satisfactory, if the spore should be re-analyzed or discarded. In total,

64.8% of WT spores were classified into single polarized, 20.7% as multiple domains 14.5% as non-polarized. Among the spores categorized as single polarized, 58.5% provided satisfactory fitting accuracy and were kept for scaling analysis.

Measurement of actin cables lengths in 3D

To selectively visualize and analyze actin cables, we disassembled actin patches by rinsing spores during 5 min with 100 μ M CK666 [S7], and immediately imaged actin cables. A putative caveat of this assay is that CK666 may have stabilizing effects on cables, limiting us to solely compare the global organization of the network in different surface geometries. Actin cables tracking was then performed in a semi-automatic manner using Imaris. Each cable was manually detected in 3D. The starting point was manually selected and a line traced along the cable while the software was selecting the focal plane corresponding to the highest fluorescence signal in the perpendicular direction. All along the tracing procedure, it was possible to rotate the image in 3D in order to avoid overlapping cables and accurately select for the one of interest. Each traced cable was then compared again by eye to the initial 3D picture, to ensure a correct detection. This detection procedure, cannot ensure that only single filaments are picked, nor detect their polarity, but is accurate enough to assess variation of network organization in different local curvature.

PDMS microchannels and -wells: Micro-channels and wells were fabricated using standard soft-lithography and PDMS methods [S8]. The PDMS channels were pierced, and washed along with a glass coverslip, with acetone, isopropanol, water, and air-dried. PDMS and glass were activated with a plasma cleaner (Harrick) and put in contact for bonding. Channels were subsequently baked for 1 h at 65°C to improve bonding. Channels have a rectangular section, are ~3 μ m deep and 2.5 μ m wide. *rga41* spores expressing CRIB-3GFP were germinated and grown for 4 h at 25°C, and a 10 μ l drop of spore suspension was then pushed into the channel hole using a syringe. This caused many spores to deform into single micro-channels, thereby adopting an ellipsoidal shape. Similar channels with varying width were used to manipulate cell diameter of vegetative cells. For this inserted spores were grown overnight in the channels; and refreshed and imaged the next morning. Usually many cells have already grown and divided into different shapes. PDMS microwells to

deform spores, had diameters ranging from 4 to 7 μm . PDMS and glass were plasma activated, a 0.5 μl of dense spore suspension was placed onto the glass slide, covered with the microwell array and gentle pressure was applied to improve spore entry into wells. For both assays on spores, pictures at different positions were rapidly recorded after spore introduction to monitor polar domain width in deformed spores.

Spheroplast protocol: Spheroplast generation was performed by using a modified Lallzyme MMX protocole [S9, S10]. Cell wall digestion was done by adding 0.1 g/ml enzyme to wild-type cells in a buffer containing 0.1M NaPhosphate, 0.1 M CiPhosphate (pH = 5.6) and 1.2 M Sorbitol at room temperature. In these conditions, most cells lost their cell wall and became round after 45 min treatment. The spheroplasts were then incubated during 2 h in EMM + supplements with 1 M sorbitol at 30 °C, and transferred onto glass slides for imaging *de novo* formed Cdc42-GTP polarity domains. For outgrowth analysis, spheroplasts were incubated for 6h at 30 °C and transferred onto agar pads for time-lapse imaging.

Visualization of active-Cdc42 domains in polarized MDCK cells. The MDCK cell line stably expressing PBD-YFP plasmid is described in [S11]. The cells were cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's high glucose medium (DMEM) (Gibco, Life Technologies) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum at 37 °C. For imaging of polarizing leader cells in gap closure, a layer of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) was pretreated with 0.2% Pluronic (Sigma), positioned in a Fluorodish, and cells were seeded at high density. The PDMS layer was removed after 18hs, when cells had filled the adhesive region, and confocal imaging was performed, in DMEM F12 (PAA) supplemented with 10% FBS, antibiotics and HEPES, to image active-Cdc42 domains in leader cells with various shapes.

STRAIN LIST

DB_301	h90	wt CRIB-3GFP:Ura	ade6-M216 leu1-32
DB_295	h90	rga4::KanMX CRIB-3GFP:Ura	ade6-M216 leu1-32
DB_292	h90	rga2::KanMX CRIB-3GFP:Ura	ade6-M216 leu1-32
DB_333	h90	for3::KanMX CRIB-3GFP:Ura	ade6-M216 leu1-32
DB_339	h90	sec8-1 CRIB-3GFP:Ura	
DB_335	h90	end4::KanMX CRIB-3GFP:Ura	ade6-M216 leu1-32
DB_351	h90	wsp1::Leu CRIB-3GFP:Ura	ade6-M216
DB_337	h90	wt CRIB-3GFP:Ura Pact1-Lamcherry:Leu	ade6-M216
DB_364	h90	for3-3GFP:Ura	ade6-M216 leu1-32
DB_378	h90	scd1-3GFP:KanMX	
DB_377	h90	scd2-GFP:NatMX	
DB_124	h90	bgs4::Ura GFP-bgs4:Leu	
DB_226	h90	CRIB-3GFP:Ura bud6-Tomato:NatMX	
DB_287	h90	CRIB-3GFP:Ura bgs4::Ura RFP-bgs4:Leu	
NM_496	h90	cdc42-mCherry-SW:KanMX CRIB-3GFP:ura	
NM_495	h90	cdc42-mCherry-SW-ritC:KanMX CRIB-3GFP:ura	
YSM2447	h90	cdc42-sfGFP-SW:KanMX (Martin Lab)	

SUPPLEMENTAL MODEL: Geometrical calculations for actin cable domes.

Based on our observation that actin cables associated with Cdc42-GTP membrane domains with a near constant nucleation density and length distribution mostly independent of local curvature, we test here mathematically how the growth of this network on differently curved surface could influence the surface covered by the network. We reason that a larger surface covered by the network may yield an increased flux of secretory vesicles attached to the network, which may dilute the domain in a dose-dependent manner. Because actin cables are highly dynamic on the time-scale of polarity domain formation, they scan on average a local surface in an isotropic manner with lengths that distribute following the measured length distribution in spores (Figure 4F). For a spherical dome made of many cables with fixed length L_{cable} , which runs along a curved surface of radius of curvature, R_c , the surface of the dome, S_{dome} , is given by:

$$S_{dome}(R_c, L_{cable}) = 2\pi R_c^2 \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{\min(L_{cable}, \pi R_c)}{R_c}\right)\right)$$

the volume is given by:

$$V_{dome}(R_c, L_{cable}) = \frac{\pi}{3} R_c^3 \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{\min(L_{cable}, \pi R_c)}{R_c}\right)\right)^2 * \left(2 + \cos\left(\frac{\min(L_{cable}, \pi R_c)}{R_c}\right)\right),$$

and the solid angle is given by:

$$\Omega_{dome}(R_c, L_{cable}) = 2\pi \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{\min(L_{cable}, \pi R_c)}{R_c}\right)\right)$$

For a given R_c we compute these geometrical values that we weight by the probability density of filament length $p(L_{cable})$ obtained experimentally (Figure 4F). For instance the mean surface explored over time by an actin dome at a radius R_c is obtained by:

$$\langle S_{dome}(R_c) \rangle = \int p(L_{cable}) S_{dome}(R_c, L_{cable})$$

By performing these calculations, we find that the mean surface of the “actin dome” increases linearly with R_c , as depicted in Figure 4G, suggesting that actin cable networks in these spores will cover a larger surface area when grown on a flat surface than on a curved one (Figure 4H). We stress that this calculation is based on a fixed measured distribution of length, and that

linearity is only valid in this range of radius. For bigger cells with different actin cable lengths; the slope or behavior could change.

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